

at panicle initiation. The WS crop received 17 kg P and 33 kg K/ha.

All the treatments received 50-22-42 kg NPK/ha during the DS to study residual effects of N.

All N levels were superior to the control during both seasons (see table).

N at 56 kg/ha equaled 84 kg N/ha; 112 kg N/ha was best during the WS. USG gave the highest yields, 3.3 t/ha in the WS and 2.9 t/ha in the DS. DS yield was low because of a hailstorm at harvest. Residual effect was pronounced

with N levels as well as sources during DS.

Bacterial blight (BB) intensity increased with increasing N, and was higher in the WS than in the DS with respect to levels as well as sources. □

Constraints to rice yields in Punjab, Pakistan

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We analyzed the contribution of various factors to the gap between potential and actual yields in farmers' field trials. The recommended inputs were land preparation by 2 plowings in dry soil and 4 plowings and 2 plankings in standing water, transplanting with 30-d-old seedlings, fertilizer at 110-26 kg NP/ha, plant density of 250,000 hills/ha, 2 kg Zn/ha, insect control using carbofuran (3G) at 16 and

20 kg/ha, and hand weeding at 20 and 30 d after transplanting.

Farmer's inputs were land preparation with 2 plowings and 1 planking in standing water, transplanting with 50-d-old seedlings, plant population of 125,000 hills/ha, fertilizer at 50-13 kg NP/ha, no Zn, no insect and weed control.

The contribution of plant density to the yield gap was 43-45% for IR6 and 55% for Basmati 370 (see figure). The contribution of fertilizer was 33-39.5% for IR6 and 27% for Basmati 370. Other test factors' contributions follow: land preparation for IR6, 22.6%; insect control (for Basmati 370), 18%; weed control, 10-17%; and seedling age (IR6), 9.7%. □

Effect of soil N on rice yield in Punjab

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We conducted 15 experiments in farmers' fields using 0, 50, 100, and 150 kg N/ha as urea, replicated twice. Surface soil samples of Typic Ustochrepts (0-15 cm) collected before transplanting were loamy sand to loam in texture, alkaline (pH 7.4 to 8.8), nonsaline (EC 0.06 to 0.48 dS/m), and low to medium in organic C (0.14 to 0.68%). The mean and range of soil test

Contribution of test factors to yield gap. Punjab, Pakistan.

Table 1. Status of nitrogen in rice growing soils. Punjab, India.

Soil N fraction	N content (µg/g soil)	
	Range	Mean
Total N	392-952	643
Hydrolyzable N	233-699	468
Hydrolyzable amino acid N	60-168	106
Hydrolyzable hexosamine N	14-56	28
Hydrolyzable NH ₄ -N	42-140	94
Nonhydrolyzable N	112-309	220

Table 2. Relationships of soil N fractions with yield and N uptake by rice. Punjab, India.

Soil N fraction	Relative yield	Relative N uptake
Total N	0.54*	0.68**
Hydrolyzable N	0.52*	0.66**
Hydrolyzable amino acid N	0.43	0.60*
Hydrolyzable hexosamine N	0.61*	0.60*
Hydrolyzable NH ₄ -N	0.64**	0.72**
Nonhydrolyzable N	0.55*	0.67**

^a Significance at the 5% (*) and 1% (**) levels.

$$\text{Relative yield/relative uptake} = \frac{\text{Yield or uptake without N}}{\text{Maximum yield or uptake with N}} \times 100.$$

values for various forms of soil N (0-15 cm depth) before transplanting are given in Table 1. The values show that a major part of organic N was present in acid hydrolyzable N form (59–74%) and nonhydrolyzable N constituted 26–41% of the total N present. Hexosamines represented 1.9–7.1% and amino acids 10.7–16.7% of total N. Hydrolyzable

NH₄-N constituted 10.6–13.9% of total N present.

Total N, hydrolyzable N, and nonhydrolyzable N correlated significantly with yield and N uptake by rice variety PR106 (Table 2). Among the forms of hydrolyzable N, NH₄-N showed the highest significant relationship with relative yield ($r =$

0.64*) and relative N uptake ($r = 0.72^{**}$), followed by hexosamine N ($r = 0.61^*$, 0.60^*) and amino acid N ($r = 0.60^*$, 0.43). Results show that forms of both hydrolyzable N and nonhydrolyzable N supply N to rice plants. Among the various fractions of soil N, hydrolyzable NH₄-N seemed to be more important. □

Rapid and sensitive method to estimate salinity tolerance of *Azolla pinnata*

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We have developed a rapid, nondestructive but sensitive method for assessing the salinity tolerance of different strains of *Azolla pinnata*. Pigments (chlorophyll and phycocyanin) are measured by their fluorescence in the heterocysts and the vegetative cells of *Anabaena azolla* isolated from sodium chloride-treated azolla, using Leitz fluorescence microscope. Chlorophyll and phycocyanin were reduced in both types of cells (see figure). The acetylene reduction activity of the *Azolla-Anabaena* complex also showed reduction, which correlated with that in the pigments of the endophyte.

Measuring the chlorophyll and phycocyanin content of *Anabaena* isolated from salt-treated azolla can be used to estimate the salinity tolerance of a particular strain of azolla. □

Effect of salinity on chlorophyll and phycocyanin of *Anabaena azollae*, and on acetylene reduction activity, Baroda, India. Sodium chloride levels: 1 = 10 mM, 2 = 20 mM, 3 = 30 mM, and 4 = 40 mM.

Effect of azolla and inorganic N combined

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We studied the effect of azolla and inorganic N on growth and yield of lowland rice variety Co 43 during 1983–84 wet and dry seasons. Soil was clay loam, with 261 kg available N/ha,

15.9 kg P/ha, 460.7 kg K/ha, and pH 7.9. The design was a randomized block with four replications. Seedlings were transplanted at 30 d at 20 × 10-cm spacing.

Prilled urea (PU) or urea supergranules (USG) alone or in combination with azolla at 75:25 were compared. N rate was 100 kg/ha for all the treatments except control. PU was split-applied: 50% basal, 25% at tillering, and 25% at panicle initiation stages;

USG was applied all basal, point placed, 1 wk after transplanting. Superphosphate at 22 kg P/ha and muriate of potash at 42 kg K/ha were basally applied. Azolla was incorporated 1 wk before transplanting.

USG at 100 kg N/ha or azolla at 25 kg N/ha with USG at 75 kg N/ha were equal in increasing dry matter production, number of panicles, grain numbers, and grain and straw yields in both seasons (see table). □